

I. Course programme

Tuesday, 09.11.2021

10.00 – 10.20	Opening Remarks	Marcus Bramow, German Police University Simon Esser, Waterways Police Hamburg
10.30 – 11.30	Legislation about mercury	Jakob Maag, United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR)
11.30 – 12.30	Lunch break	
12.30 – 13.30	Forensic tools for detection and investigation of waste and mercury crime	Marion Stelling, Netherlands Forensic Institute (NFI)
14.00 – 15.00	Investigation of illegal waste shipment in German Federal criminal police office	Andreas Windolph, German Federal Criminal Police Office (BKA)

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10.00 – 11.00	STRIKE guidelines	Elena D'Angelo UNITAR
11.00 – 12.00	Collaboration between district government of lower Bavaria, Bavarian police service and German Customs	Katharina Aiblinger-Madersbacher District Government of Lower Bavaria
12.00 – 13.00	Lunch break	
13.00 – 14.00	Illegal waste shipment from a customs investigation perspective	Dietmar Möllmann, Central Customs Investigation Office (ZKA)

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Thursday, 11.11.2021

10.00 – 11.00	Shipbreaking- what is it about, what are the threats for human beings and the environment and what are the relevant laws?	Ingvild Jenssen, NGO shipbreaking platform
11.00 – 12.00	Case studies in the field of illegal shipbreaking	Katie Olley, Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA)
12.00 – 13.00	Lunch break	

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13.00 – 14.15

Joint investigations in international cases of ship breaking

Dirk Schwartz, Waterways Police Hamburg

Hartmut Neumann, German Waterways Police
Reporting and Coordination Centre/
Maritime Safety and Security Centre

14.30 – 15.00

Wrapping up and farewell

Marcus Bramow, German Police University

Simon Esser, Waterways Police Hamburg